

Posit Arithmetic Units for Deep Neural Networks

Raul Murillo, Alberto A. Del Barrio and Guillermo Botella¹

Abstract—PositTM arithmetic is a recent alternative format to the IEEE 754 standard for floating-point numbers that claims to provide compelling advantages over floats, including higher accuracy, larger dynamic range or bitwise compatibility across systems. In particular, this format is a suitable candidate to replace floating-point numbers in Deep Neural Networks (DNNs), an area of growing interest with a large computational cost. This work presents parameterized designs for multiple posit functional units, including addition, multiplication and multiply-accumulate operation, and integrate them as templates of the FloPoCo framework. Synthesis results show that the proposed arithmetic units significantly reduce the hardware requirements when compared with previous implementations. Finally, this work proposes the use of posit arithmetic for performing both DNN inference and training. Experiments on different datasets, including CIFAR-10, reveal that 16-bit posits can safely replace 32-bit floats for training, and that low-precision 8-bit posits can be used for DNN inference with negligible accuracy drop.

Keywords—Computer Arithmetic, Posit, Floating-point, Adder, Multiplier, Deep Neural Networks.

I. INTRODUCTION

DEEP Neural Networks (DNNs) dominate nowadays machine learning landscape due to the great advances in a large variety of applications, including computer vision, natural language processing or speech recognition. Typically, deep learning tasks are computationally expensive, specially during the training phase, which requires substantial energy consumption. In fact, GPUs have been the key component for much DNN processing in the last decade, and there is an increasingly interest in providing more specialized acceleration of the DNN computation [1, 2]. For this reason, reducing the computational complexity of DNNs to perform inference on resource-constraint devices has been a serious challenge and a lengthy line of research [3].

The IEEE 754 standard for floating-point arithmetic [4] has been for decades the de facto implementation for the vast majority of scientific computing and real number-based applications. However, over the years diverse problems have been encountered with the standard floating-point numbers, or floats, such as rounding and reproducibility issues, signed zero or excess of NaN representations [5].

Recently, several computer arithmetic encodings and formats, including high-precision anchored numbers from ARM, half-precision arithmetic, bfloat16, etc. have been considered as an alternative to IEEE 754-2008 compliant arithmetic [6]. But probably, one of the most promising contributions is the Posit

Number System (PNS) [7]. Several research efforts have investigated the application of posit arithmetic and its benefits in a wide variety of areas such as climate modeling [8], neural networks [9], or linear algebra [10].

The PNS offers compelling advantages over the IEEE 754 floating-point format. Under the same bitwidth, posits provide a better trade-off than floats between dynamic range and decimal accuracy. What is more, it has been shown that an n -bit floating-point adder/multiplier could be safely replaced by an m -bit posit adder/multiplier where $m < n$ [11]. In addition, posit arithmetic includes just two special cases (single 0 and $\pm\infty$), which simplifies the hardware designs, uses a single rounding scheme (round to nearest, ties to even), solving the reproducibility issue mentioned for IEEE 754 floats, and the standard introduces the so-called *fused operations*, which allow to perform computations with more than two operands (such as the dot product, which is the core operation in DNNs) without intermediate rounding, thus reducing the error of such computations. However, posit arithmetic is still in an early stage of development, and the lack of hardware support for this novel format hinders its use in computer-intensive applications.

This work proposes the design of posit arithmetic units and its application in DNNs. Artificial neurons, the basic building-block of DNNs, mainly perform weighted sums. Therefore, this work focuses on the design of posit addition, multiplication, and fused dot-product units.

The rest of the paper is organized as follows. Section II reviews preliminary concepts about posit arithmetic as well as previous hardware implementations. Section III presents the designs of posit functional units, and those are evaluated in Section IV. The performance of posit and floating-point arithmetic in DNNs applications are analyzed in Section V. Finally, the concluding remarks of this work are presented in Section VI.

II. BACKGROUND

A. The Posit Number System

A posit format is defined as a tuple $\langle n, es \rangle$, where n is the total bitwidth and es is the maximum number of bits reserved for the exponent field. As Fig. 1 shows, posit numbers are encoded with four fields: a sign bit (s), several bits for encoding the regime value (k), up to es bits for the exponent (e), and the remaining bits for fraction (f). Thus, the numerical value X of a generic Posit $\langle n, es \rangle$ is expressed by (1).

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Fig. 1: Layout of an $\text{Posit}(n, es)$ number.

$$X = (-1)^s \times (2^{2^{es}})^k \times 2^e \times (1 + f), \quad (1)$$

$$k = -x_{n-2} + \sum_{i=n-2}^{x_i \neq x_{n-2}} (-1)^{1-x_i}. \quad (2)$$

The main differences with floating-point format are the utilization of an unsigned and unbiased exponent, if there exists such exponent field, and the existence of the regime field. This new field consists of a sequence of bits with the same value finished with the negation of such value, as shown in Fig. 1. Provided that $X = x_{n-1}x_{n-2}\dots x_1x_0$, this regime can be expressed as (2) shows. The variable-length regime field may cause the exponent to be encoded with less than es bits, or even with no bits if regime is wide enough. The same occurs with the fraction field.

It is noteworthy that, while the new regime field provides important scaling capabilities that improve the dynamic range of posits, detecting the resulting varying-sized fields adds a hardware overhead. Finally, the posit format just considers two special cases, 0 and infinity, or Not-a-Real (NaN). These exceptions are encoded with all the bits except the leftmost equal to 0, and the sign bit indicates if the posit value is zero (sign bit is 0) or NaN (sign bit is 1). Note that this simplifies hardware design with respect the IEEE 754 standard, which includes signed representations of zero and infinity, as well as multiple bit patterns for representing NaN exceptions.

B. Related Work

Since the PNS was introduced in 2017, the interest in scenarios where posits can outperform floats has increased rapidly. In particular, this novel format seems very promising in the field of deep learning. In [12], J. Johnson designed an arithmetic unit for combining posit addition together with logarithmic multiplication for inference in convolutional neural networks. Authors in [13] employ a posit DNN accelerator to represent weights and activations combined with an FPGA soft core for 8-bit posit exact multiply-accumulate (MAC) operations. In all these works, DNN training is performed in floating-point, while the inference stage is performed in low-precision posit format. Later works proposed different approaches for training DNNs using the PNS, either directly training on this format with different precision [9,14], or with the help of a warm-up training using floating-point format [15].

The main problematic with the PNS is that there is currently no available hardware support for this format. For this reason, the interest on hardware implementations for this format has increased rapidly,

and different approaches have been proposed so far. Authors in [16] proposed open-source parameterized designs for posit addition and multiplication. These operators are not compatible with the standard since they do not perform proper rounding. The authors expanded this work into a posit core generator called PACoGen [17], which improved the previous designs and included posit division. Other parameterized designs of posit arithmetic units were presented in [11, 18, 19]. However, the community is still in the early stages of research into posit arithmetic, and as a result, posit hardware is currently slightly more costly than floating-point hardware.

III. DESIGN OF POSIT FUNCTIONAL UNITS

The proposed posit arithmetic units are discussed in this section. At hardware level, posits were designed to be easy to compute, i.e., to have a circuitry similar to the existing floating point. The main encoding differences between float and posit formats are the fact that the second one includes a run-time varying scaling component and that the fraction implicit bit is always 1.

A. Posit Decoding

Due to the variable-length fields of the posit format, the operand fields decoding flow slightly differs from the analogous stage for IEEE 754 numbers. The proposed posit decoding process is presented in Algorithm 1. First, the sign bit (MSB) is extracted, and special cases (zero or NaN) are detected performing OR reduce on the remaining $n - 1$ bits. In case the input posit value is negative, the absolute value of the posit is obtained via 2's complement, simplifying the data extraction process and future operations such as addition of two posits. Then, the regime is computed and shifted-out. Finally, the exponent bits (if any) and fraction fields are extracted from the shifted bits. The regime and exponent are gathered into a scaling factor (sf) to simplify subsequent operations.

B. Posit Encoding & Rounding

The pseudocode of posit output process is presented in Algorithm 2. Firstly, the scaling factor is split into regime and exponent. The former is converted to positive to detect the overflow exception. Final posit value is obtained by right-shifting the exponent and fraction according to the regime value and its sign (rs). Posits, same as IEEE 754 floats, follow round-to-nearest-even scheme. Therefore, the Guard (G), Round (R) and Sticky (S) bits must be computed to perform a correct unbiased rounding. Finally, the result is obtained considering the final sign bit and special cases.

C. Posit Addition

The addition of two posits, depicted in Fig. 2 is similar to how it is performed in the IEEE 754 floating-point numbers. First, the larger and smaller operands are detected. It must be noted that posit

Algorithm 1 Posit data extraction

Require: $X \in \text{Posit}\langle n, es \rangle$ **Ensure:** $X = (-1)^{\text{sign}} \times 2^{\text{sf}} \times (1 + \text{frac})$, or $\text{nzn} = 0$

```
1:  $\text{sign} \leftarrow X[n-1]$ 
2:  $\text{nzn} \leftarrow \text{OR}(X[n-2:0])$   $\triangleright$  OR reduce
3:  $\text{p\_abs} \leftarrow (X[n-2:0] \oplus \text{sign}) + \text{sign}$ 
4:  $\text{rs} \leftarrow \text{p\_abs}[n-2]$   $\triangleright$  Regime sign
5:  $\text{shifted}, \text{count} \leftarrow \text{LZOC} + \text{Shift}(\text{p\_abs}, \text{rs})$ 
6:  $\text{frac} \leftarrow \text{shifted}[n-es-4:0]$ 
7: if  $\text{rs} == 0$  then
8:    $\text{reg} \leftarrow -\text{count}$ 
9: else
10:   $\text{reg} \leftarrow \text{count} - 1$ 
11: end if
12: if  $es > 0$  then
13:   $\text{exp} \leftarrow \text{shifted}[n-2:n-es-1]$ 
14:   $\text{sf} \leftarrow \{\text{reg}, \text{exp}\}$ 
15: else
16:   $\text{sf} \leftarrow \text{reg}$ 
17: end if
18: return  $\text{sign}, \text{sf}, \text{frac}, \text{nzn}, \text{p\_abs}$ 
```

Algorithm 2 Posit data encoding

Require: $\text{sign}, \text{sf}, \text{frac}, \text{nzn}$ fields of R **Ensure:** $R \in \text{Posit}\langle n, es \rangle$ and is correctly rounded

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1: if  $es > 0$  then
2:   $\text{exp} \leftarrow \text{sf}[es-1:0]$ 
3:   $\text{ls\_bits} \leftarrow \{\text{exp}, \text{frac}\}$ 
4: else
5:   $\text{ls\_bits} \leftarrow \text{frac}$ 
6: end if
7:  $\text{rs} \leftarrow \text{sf}[\text{MSB}-1]$ 
8: if  $\text{rs} == 1$  then  $\triangleright$  Get regime's absolute value
9:   $\text{reg} \leftarrow -\text{sf}[\text{MSB}-1:es]$ 
10: else
11:   $\text{reg} \leftarrow \text{sf}[\text{MSB}-1:es]$ 
12: end if
13: if  $\text{reg} > n-2$  then
14:   $\text{reg} \leftarrow n-2$   $\triangleright$  Regime overflow
15: end if
16:  $\text{in\_shf} \leftarrow \{-\text{rs}, \text{rs}, \text{ls\_bits}\}$ 
17:  $\text{offset} \leftarrow \text{reg} - \text{rs}$ 
18:  $\text{ans\_shf} \leftarrow \text{in\_shf} \gg (\text{offset}, -\text{rs})$ 
19:  $\text{ans\_tmp} \leftarrow \text{ans\_shf}[\text{MSB}-1:\text{MSB}-(n-1)]$ 
20:  $G, R \leftarrow \text{ans\_shf}[\text{MSB}-(n-1):\text{MSB}-(n)]$ 
21:  $S \leftarrow \text{OR}(\text{ans\_shf}[\text{MSB}-(n+1):0])$ 
22:  $\text{round} \leftarrow R \wedge (G \vee S)$ 
23: if  $\text{nzn} == 1$  then
24:   $\text{result} \leftarrow ((\text{ans\_tmp} + \text{round}) \oplus \text{sign}) + \text{sign}$ 
25: else  $\triangleright$  Special cases, all 0's
26:   $\text{result} \leftarrow \{n-1\{0\}\}$ 
27: end if
28:  $R \leftarrow \{\text{sign}, \text{result}\}$ 
29: return  $R$ 
```

comparison can be done as integers. The fraction of the smaller operand is right shifted (according to the difference of scaling factors of both operands) prior to being added/subtracted to the largest one. Then, the leading zeros of the resulting fraction are shifted out

Fig. 2: Architecture of a posit adder.

Fig. 3: Architecture of a posit multiplier.

to get a normalized field. The final sign and scaling factor are taken from the larger operand, subtracting the number of leading zeros from the fraction and adding one in case it is overflowed. Note that since operands are previously decoded, subtraction operation just differs on flipping a sign bit before performing the addition flow.

D. Posit Multiplication

The posit multiplication process (Fig. 3) starts by detecting the output sign and corner cases. The fractions are multiplied as usually, and the most significant bit of such multiplication is used for both normalizing the result and as carry bit for the addition of scaling factors.

E. Posit Exact Multiplication and Accumulation

The posit standard [20] introduces the possibility to perform fused operations, i.e., operations with more than two operands in which the rounding is deferred until the entire expression is evaluated. To

1 bit	C bits	$1+(n-2)\times 2^{es+1}$ bits	$(n-2)\times 2^{es+1}$ bits
Sign	Carry ward	Integer	Fraction

Fig. 4: Binary quire format.

avoid intermediate rounding, posits make use of the so-called *quire*, a large Kulisch-like accumulator [21] that represents numbers in fixed-point 2's complement. Fig. 4 illustrates the format of a quire for $\text{Posit}\langle n, es \rangle$. The integer and fraction parts must be able to represent the product of any two posits in fixed-point format. After the sign bit, the additional C carry bits allow to perform up to 2^C product sums without risk of overflow. In quire format, NaN special value is represented with all zeros except the first bit, as in the case of posits.

The MAC operation using the quire accumulator is able to perform exact sums of products without introducing intermediate rounding errors. Therefore, this operation requires three operands, two posits that will be multiplied as described in previous section, and a quire where to accumulate the unrounded multiplication. The result from multiplication must be converted into quire format. This is done by shifting the multiplied fractions certain number of bits given by the resulting scaling factor. Finally, both quires can be added without loss of accuracy.

IV. HARDWARE EVALUATION

The posit arithmetic designs presented in this paper have been implemented into FloPoCo, an open-source C++ framework for the generation of arithmetic datapaths that provides a command-line interface that inputs operator specifications and outputs synthesizable VHDL [22]. This tool allows operators to be automatically generated with the specified parameters and, therefore, to obtain posit operators for arbitrary values of $\langle n, es \rangle$ with the same base design. The operators have been verified for multiple posit configurations with the reference SoftPosit library¹. Sources to reproduce this experiment are publicly available² and scripts are included in the official FloPoCo repository.

Standard cell synthesis has been performed using Synopsys Design Compiler with a 45-nm library by TSMC for the proposed generated units. These operators have been compared with the state-of-the-art designs from Posit-HDL-Arithmetic [16]³ and PACoGen [17]⁴ for posit addition and multiplication, and with the MAC unit from Deep Positron [13]⁵. The results for $es = 2$ (and 30 carry bits in the case of MAC) are compared graphically in Figs. 5, 6 and 7. Similar results are obtained for different parameters. As can be seen, the proposed designs provide an overall reduction of area and power with respect

¹gitlab.com/cerlane/SoftPosit.

²github.com/RaulMurillo/Flo-Posit.

³Source code obtained from github.com/manish-kj/Posit-HDL-Arithmetic/tree/3065c2e.

⁴Source code obtained from github.com/manish-kj/PACoGen/tree/5f6572c.

⁵Source code obtained from github.com/craymichael/Low-Precision-EMACs/tree/b6fe0d1.

Fig. 5: $\text{Posit}\langle n, 2 \rangle$ and floating-point adder implementation results.

Fig. 6: $\text{Posit}\langle n, 2 \rangle$ and floating-point multiplier implementation results.

previous implementations. With respect to the datapath delay of the operators, while the multiplier gets similar results as PACoGen (but worse than Posit-HDL), the proposed adder worsens in this respect compared to previous work. Despite this, energy consumption, which is the power–delay product, is in both cases lower for the proposed operators than for those from PACoGen, being very similar to that obtained with the Posit-HDL operators. However, it is important to recall that operators from Posit-HDL perform fraction truncation instead of proper rounding. Regarding MAC units, the proposed design provides remarkable reduction in terms of area and delay with respect Deep Positron implementation, especially when the bitwidth is greater than 16. It must be noted that, while the proposed MAC unit returns the result in quire format, the Deep Positron one outputs the result in posit format, adding extra hardware for quire-to-posit conversion in the same operator. Finally, analogous floating-point adder and multiplier units have been generated for half (float16) and single (float32) precision with FloPoCo. Synthesis results show that posit arithmetic units are still far from being competitive in comparison with floating-point units. Nonetheless, it is important to recall that floating-point designs provided by this tool are not fully IEEE 754 compliant, since they do not include support for denormalized numbers or full exception handling and therefore use less resources.

Fig. 7: Posit($n, 2$) and floating-point multiply-accumulator implementation results.

V. EVALUATING POSIT ARITHMETIC IN DNNs

To evaluate the performance of the posit arithmetic, different DNNs architectures and datasets of reference for image classification are considered at both inference and training. LeNet-5 [23] is a well-known Convolutional network that provides nice performance on greyscale-image datasets such as MNIST and Fashion-MNIST. For RGB-images datasets like SVHN or CIFAR-10, deeper networks as CifarNet [24] are recommended.

As in most deep learning frameworks, training is done under IEEE 754 single-precision floating-point format (float32), while half-precision floats or 8-bit integers are used for low-precision inference. Previous works from literature recommend the use of 32-bit or even 16-bit posit numbers, arguing that the latter could be safely replace 32-bit floats. Due to the lack of hardware support, in this work the computations within DNNs are performed with Deep PeN-Sieve, an open-source framework that allows to generate DNN models and perform inference and training entirely using posits [9]. Deep PeNSieve relies on the reference library SoftPosit, which ensures that these software operations behave like the operators proposed in Section III. This framework also allows to perform fused dot-product with quire, which relies on the operation described in Section III, for 8-bit posits at inference stage. Reducing the precision format of trained DNNs, also known as quantization, is a widely used technique for performing inference which reduces the computational cost of the models while slightly decreasing their accuracy.

A. DNN training

Table I shows comparisons among the inference results of standard float32 and posits on different trained models. As can be seen, models trained with PNS present similar results than the baseline float32. Moreover, networks employing Posit(16, 1) show higher accuracy than 32-bit formats, especially for the complex CIFAR-10 dataset, where Top-1 is more than 4% higher than that obtained with float32. While this is a very significant improvement, it does not mean yet that posits behave better than

floats, but provide similar performance as floats with less number of bits. For the sake of completeness, regularization techniques, such as batch normalization or dropout, should be ported to the PNS as well, although this escapes the scope of this work. Besides the accuracy, it is important to note the model size reduction of low-precision formats: while 32-bit models require 724 KB and 21 MB when stored on disk for LeNet-5 and CifarNet, respectively, models on Posit(16, 1) format require just 362 KB and 10.5 MB, respectively. Thus, with the corresponding posit hardware support the use of 16-bits posits would reduce the memory usage of the NNs, enabling training larger models or with larger mini-batches [25].

Table I: Accuracy results (%) after the training stage

Format	MNIST		Fashion-MNIST		SVHN		CIFAR-10	
	Top-1	Top-5	Top-1	Top-5	Top-1	Top-5	Top-1	Top-5
Float32	99.17	100	89.34	99.78	89.32	98.35	68.06	95.15
Posit(32, 2)	99.09	99.98	89.90	99.84	89.51	98.36	69.32	96.59
Posit(16, 1)	99.18	100	90.17	99.81	90.90	98.72	72.51	97.40

B. DNN post-training quantization

The previously trained models are kept unchanged in order to perform low-precision inference. Then, common quantization methods for float32 and Posit(32, 2) models are compared. For the floating-point case, float16 quantization and integer quantization techniques are employed to obtain models that entirely work in float16 and INT8 formats, respectively. With regard to posits, the 32-bit models have been quantized to Posit(8, 0). Moreover, this work compares inference results between naive posit quantization and employing the 8-bit posit fused dot-product with quire approach. The inference results for the different post-training quantization techniques are shown in Table II. Note that quantized 16-bit and 8-bit models are, respectively, 1/2 and 1/4 the size of the corresponding original 32-bit models. Results confirm the potential of conventional quantization techniques. Nevertheless, it is well-known that for larger networks such as MobileNet, integer quantization provides higher accuracy degradation [26]. On the other hand, there is a notable difference in the posits case between using quire and fused operations or not. Networks using fused dot product with quire get much higher accuracy (25% higher Top-1 for CIFAR-10) as not using, and this difference becomes more noticeable with more complex networks. In the worst case, on CIFAR-10 dataset, accuracy degradation of Posit(8, 0)_{quire} is just 0.44% with respect to the original 32-bits model, which is more than acceptable.

VI. CONCLUSIONS

The recent advances on DNNs throughout the last decade have made them critical for many AI applications, including computer vision, speech recognition, and robotics, and providing even better performance than human being in many situations. However,

Table II: Post-training quantization accuracy results (%) for the inference stage

Format	MNIST		Fashion-MNIST		SVHN		CIFAR-10	
	Top-1	Top-5	Top-1	Top-5	Top-1	Top-5	Top-1	Top-5
Float16	99.17	100	89.34	99.78	89.32	98.35	68.05	96.15
INT8	99.16	100	89.51	99.79	89.33	98.38	68.15	96.14
Posit(8, 0)	98.77	99.99	88.52	99.82	81.31	97.07	43.89	86.49
Posit(8, 0) _{quire}	99.07	99.99	89.92	99.81	89.13	98.39	68.88	96.47

while DNNs can deliver this outstanding accuracy, it comes at the cost of high computational complexity. In this area, posits are presented as ideal candidates to replace floats, providing the same precision with a smaller bitwidth.

Due to the short life of posits, the design of arithmetic units for this format is still at an early stage of development. To date, few such designs have been proposed, even less open-source. This work proposes parameterized algorithms for performing addition and multiplication of posits. Such algorithms have been integrated into the FloPoCo framework in order to obtain synthesizable VHDL code for any bitwidth and exponent size configuration. Results show a great improvement in terms of area, power and energy consumption with respect to the state-of-the-art works. The performance of posits has been evaluated on the training and inference of various DNNs. Experiments reveal that directly training with posits gets better results than training with floating-point and quantizing to posits. Additionally, the proposed posit quantization with fused dot-product outperforms naive posit quantization presented in previous works.

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